

Original Research

Comparison of functional outcome of arthroscopic ACL reconstruction between adjustable closed loop and endobutton for femoral fixation of quadrupled hamstring autograft

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Cortical suspension devices have been widely used in ACL reconstruction for femoral side graft fixation. Fixed-length and adjustable-length loop devices are two common suspensory loop devices that are used in ACL reconstruction. They both have their own biomechanical pros and cons. The purpose of this study is to determine the difference in functional outcome of anatomical single bundle ACL reconstruction using fixed length versus adjustable length loop in femoral fixation of quadrupled hamstring graft. **Material and methods:** It is a longitudinal prospective study conducted in various military hospitals of Indian army. There were 60 patients enrolled in the study. The first 30 patients were treated with Arthroscopic ACL reconstruction with quadrupled hamstring graft from ipsilateral limb fixed with Endobutton on femoral side and bio-absorbable interference tibial screw, similarly in subsequent 30 patients ACL reconstruction were treated with quadrupled hamstring graft from ipsilateral limb fixed with closed adjustable loop on femoral side and bio-absorbable interference tibial screw. Their clinical and functional status were assessed pre-operatively on the day prior to surgery and the last follow up at one following the surgery with Tegner-Lysholm Score and 2000 IKDC scores. **Results:** The average pre operative Tegner- Lysholm score before surgery in Endobutton group was 56.63±6.7 and post op score at last follow up was 93.97±4.1 and for closed adjustable loop group it was 56.5±7.1 and 94.7±3.7 respectively. The average 2000 IKDC score before surgery in Endobutton group was 46.16±6.1 and postop score at last follow up was 82.52±4.2 and for closed adjustable loop group it was 46.57±6.5 and 83.98±4.1 respectively. Two sample student t-test was conducted to compare the mean of post-operative Tegner-Lysholm score and 2000 IKDC for each group it showed P value for Tegner-Lysholm score to be 0.75 and that for 2000 IKDC score to be 0.7, which not statistically significant to reject the null hypothesis. **Conclusion:** Cortical suspension devices for femoral tunnel graft fixation are very efficient devices whether Fixed-length or adjustable length. Fixed-length and adjustable loop cortical suspension devices are equally effective in femoral fixation of graft in ACL reconstruction.

Key words: Anterior cruciate ligament, cortical suspension device, Fixed-length loop device, Adjustable length loop device.

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INTRODUCTION

ACL injury is one of the most common injuries of knee among the high level athletes which account for nearly about 50% of total knee injury. It is also common in young and active nonsports people. Its prevalence is estimated to be 1 in 3000 in the United States (greater than 120 000 cases annually).¹ Anatomical ACL reconstruction has become the gold standard for the treatment of ACL tear to return patients to pre-injury status and to prevent instability

and long term OA knee.² The use of the semitendinosus and gracilis (STG) tendons is becoming the choice method in anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) reconstruction. This graft, with four strands of STG tightened identically, presents the advantage of having a mechanical resistance theoretically superior to the mechanical resistance of a tendon from the patellar ligament with a minimum width of 10mm, having a minimum of iatrogenic complications, preserving the extensor apparatus and

thus reducing anterior knee pain. A wide variety of fixation solutions to attach the hamstring tendons have been proposed. Most commonly used devices for femoral fixation are interference screws, transfix screws and cortical suspension devices. Devices for tibial fixation can be divided according to the location of fixation: intratunnel fixation and extratunnel fixation. Intratunnel fixation methods primarily rely on the metallic or bioresorbable interference screw, a relatively novel approach called Intrafix, or a cross pin system.³ Cortical suspension devices have been widely used in ACL reconstruction for femoral side graft fixation. Various studies have shown that cortical suspension devices have the necessary biomechanical properties with regard to ultimate failure strength, displacement, and stiffness for initial fixation of soft tissue in the femoral tunnel for ACL reconstruction.⁴⁻⁶ Cortical suspension devices are available in two varieties 1. Fixed Loop-length device e. g. Endobutton and 2. Adjustable Loop-length device e. g. Tightrope. Endobutton is the first generation suspensory fixation with fixed-length loop. The length of the loop is fixed but it is stiffer and slippage-free which seems to have created a more favourable biomechanical environment. closed adjustable loop is the second generation suspensory fixation device with the adjustable-length loop which is reduced after flipping by tightening the rope. It allows full length filling of graft part of the femoral tunnel and some degree of final tightening to tension the graft even after placement of the graft. This seems to be the theoretical advantage of tightrope over endobutton which remove final slack off the knee after the placement of the graft and prevent long term laxity of the reconstructed knee. But experimental studies has shown that allows full length filling of graft part of the femoral tunnel and some degree of final tightening to tension the graft even after placement of the graft.⁷ The purpose of this study is to determine the difference in functional outcome following anatomical single bundle ACL reconstruction using these techniques.

Hypothesis

There no difference in clinical outcome following ACL reconstruction between fixed-length loop and adjustable length cortical suspension devices used for femoral side fixation.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

It is a longitudinal prospective study conducted in various Military Hospitals of Indian army from, August 2016 to February 2018. The sample was collected from January 2014 to February 2018. There were 60 patients enrolled in the study. The first 30 patients were treated with Arthroscopic ACL reconstruction in the first 30 patients were done with quadrupled hamstring graft from ipsilateral limb fixed with Endobutton on femoral side and bio-absorbable interference tibial screw, similarly in subsequent 30

patients ACL reconstruction were done with quadrupled hamstring graft from ipsilateral limb fixed with Endobutton on femoral side and bio-absorbable interference tibial screw. Postoperative rehabilitation protocols were same for both the group. Their clinical and functional status were assessed preoperatively on the day prior to surgery with Tegner-Lysholm Score and 2000 IKDC scores and at the last follow up at least one year following the surgery. The last follow up date was 31st July 2016. Data entry was done in Microsoft excel 2010. Mean and standard deviation were calculated for all categorical data. Two sample-t test was used to compare the mean of two group.

RESULTS

There were 60 patients included in the study 30 in Endobutton group and closed adjustable loop group. Age of the patients in Endobutton group ranged from 19 years to 53 years with mean age of 33.3 ± 18.2 years and in closed adjustable loop group it ranges from 19 years to 51 years with mean age of 31 ± 20 . The range of follow up duration for Endobutton group were 18 months to 30 months with mean follow up duration of 21.3 ± 8.6 . Similarly, that of closed adjustable loop group was 12 months to 18 months with mean follow up duration of 14.16 ± 5.5 months. The average Tegner-Lysolm score before surgery in Endobutton group was 56.63 ± 6.7 and post op score at last follow up was 93.97 ± 4.1 and for Tightrope group it was 56.5 ± 7.1 and 94.7 ± 3.7 respectively. The average 2000 IKDC score before surgery in Endobutton group was 46.16 ± 6.1 and post-op score at last follow up was 82.52 ± 4.2 and for closed adjustable loop group it was 46.57 ± 6.5 and 83.98 ± 4.1 respectively. Two sample student t-test was conducted to compare the mean of post-operative Tegner-Lysolm score and 2000 IKDC for each group it showed P value for Tegner-Lysolm score to be 0.75 and that for 2000 IKDC score to be 0.7 which not statistically significant to reject the null hypothesis.

DISCUSSION

Cortical suspension device has been one of the most widely used for femoral fixation of quadrupled hamstring graft in ACL reconstruction. These devices have ultimate failure strength greater than that necessary for early ACL rehabilitation for clinical use in ACL femoral fixation. It consists of a button that rests on the femoral cortex and a loop that hold the folded graft in position until healing occur. Controversy still exists whether fixed-length loop is better than adjustable-length loop for femoral fixation if cortical suspension device is used. Fixed-length devices have high failure strength but tunnel has to be over drilled to flip the button on the femoral cortex create a potential space between the graft and the bone. This potential space can cause "Bungee effect" eventually leading to tunnel widening and graft failure. Adjustable-length loop devices were designed to overcome this disadvantage of fixed-length loop

devices. Biomechanical studies has shown that Adjustable-length ACL graft cortical suspension devices lengthen under cyclic loads because free suture ends are pulled into the adjustable loop.^{8,9} Watson J conducted a review of 4 articles in 2014. All those studies provided the mechanical testing of the adjustablelength versus fixed-length loop devices using cyclic loading within the range considered normal for normal ACL undergoing basic activities of daily living. He found significantly less displacement for fixed-length loop than for adjustable-length design and had a higher tensile strength. He concluded from his study that adjustable-length loop could slip and elongate under load after they had been adjusted to their minimum length which might lead to delayed graft healing and joint instability.¹⁰ Pasquali M et al. conducted a comparative study on three adjustable cortical suspension devices for the femoral fixation of graft to see the displacement on cyclic loading and failure strength. Their study showed both Arthrex's Tight Rope RT (TR), and DePuyMitek's RIGIDLOOP Adjustable (RLA showed clinically acceptable amounts of cyclic displacement and maximum strength.¹¹ In our study we compared the patients based outcome measure using Endobutton as fixed-length loop femoral fixation device and adjustable-length loop device. We found there was significant improvement in the clinical and functional status in both the group after operation. But there were no clinically significant changes in outcome between the groups. Both the implant showed similar outcome whatever be their experimental advantages and disadvantages. Boyle MJ et al. conducted a retrospective study of 188 patients who underwent primary ACL reconstruction using hamstrings autograft. They performed ACLR with adjustableloop (Tightrope RT (ArthrexInc, Naples, FL) in 73 patients and with fixed-loop (RetroButton (ArthrexInc, Naples, FL)) femoral cortical suspension in 115 patients. They followed up their patients for 2 years and they found no difference in clinical outcome between the two devices.¹² Choi et al. conducted retrospective study to compare clinical outcomes and tunnel widening after hamstring ACL reconstructions with fixed-and adjustable-loop cortical suspension device. They took total of 117 consecutive patients who underwent hamstring ACL reconstruction at a single institution. The fixed-loop cortical suspension device was used in 67 patients, and the adjustable-loop cortical suspension device was used in 50 patients. All patients were observed for a minimum of 2 years. They found that femoral fixation by use of the fixed-loop device or femoral fixation by use of the adjustable-loop device showed similar clinical outcomes but did not reduce tunnel widening after hamstring ACL reconstructions.¹³ Author found additional advantages of adjustable length device that final tightening of the graft could be done after tibial fixation of the graft which reassured the adequate tensioning of graft. Similar observation has been

mentioned in the article," Biomechanical evaluation of an adjustable loop suspensory anterior cruciate ligament reconstruction fixation device: the value of retensioning and knot tying." by Noonan BC et al. They found increase cyclic elongation in adjustable length loop device more than fixed-length loop but it was easily eliminated by retensioning and knot tying. So they believed that retensioning and knot tying after initial reduction of graft with adjustable loop ACL fixation device might help to further reduce concerns of loop slippage and displacement with cyclic loading during post-operative rehabilitation.¹⁴

CONCLUSION

Cortical suspension devices for femoral tunnel graft fixation are very efficient devices whether Fixed-length or adjustable length. Fixed-length and adjustable loop cortical suspension devices are equally effective in femoral fixation of graft in ACL reconstruction. Limitation of the Study The minimum follow up period for Tightrope group is only one year

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